

FINAL PROJECT REPORT

PROJECT TITLE: Computer aided drug
designing platform towards the enigma
SARS-CoV-2 spike protein of COVID-19

INSTITUTION NAME: UNIVERSITY OF SOFIA, FACULTY OF CHEMISTRY AND
PHARMACY

Street Address Blvd James Bourchier 1

City and Zip Sofia 1164

[HTTPS://WWW.UNI-SOFIA.BG/INDEX.PHP/ENG](https://www.uni-sofia.bg/index.php/eng)

PROJECT NUMBER 202/02.10.2020 – 31.03.2021

APPROVED AMOUNT: 40.000, 00 EUR

TRANSFER: 50% - 20.000,00 EUR

WORKING PAKAGES

	Title	DESCRIPTION OF CHANGE
WP1	- Project Management will undertake coordination activities in the project and overall guidance; also, the WP will guarantee that all control and reporting mechanisms are being applied according to the Quality Assurance Procedures.	NA
WP2 – Chemoinformatics Framework	WP2 – Chemoinformatics Framework Development for the drug database based on chemical descriptors and Pharmacophore modelling	NA
WP3 -	Chemical similarity analysis and Machine learning models in QSAR.	The general protocol for pattern recognition between the drug candidates was based on chemoinformatics and machine learning techniques.
WP 4	Druggability Assessment	Assessment was done by the docking simulation protocol.
WP 5	Molecular Dynamics	NA
WP 6	Definition, Setting Up and Running of the Platform will use the information gathered from the previous WP to specify, develop and deploy the information in the Communication Platform.	NA
WP 7	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation	NA

TEAM MEMBERS AND RESPONSIBILITIES

NAME	ROLE	RESPONSIBILITIES
Miroslava Nedyalkova	Team Lider	WP2-WP7
Sergio Madurga	Member	WP5, WP7
Haruna Luz Barazorda Ccahuana	Member	WP5, WP7
Subramanyam Sappati	Member	WP5, WP4,WP7
. Mahdi Vasigh	Member	WP3, WP4, WP7
Julia Romanova	Member	WP3,WP7
Vasil Simeonov	Member	WP3,WP4,WP7

1. PROJECT SUMMARY

" The emergence and rapid worldwide spread of the novel coronavirus disease, COVID-19, has prompted concerted efforts to find successful treatments. The causative virus, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) – a strain of severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus. The discovery of new drugs that could target this complex efficiently would be a very long, multi-step and expensive process as every other drug discovery.

We propose a workflow of combined in silico, cheminformatics methods and Machine learning that will be used to predict and identify novel drug by screening from the available data which are deposit in chemical libraries consisting of FDA approved or test drugs, and as well the nature compound based on essential oils and available information in the literature sources to select compounds interacting with spike protein (PDB: 6VYB).

Work plan

WP1 - Project Management will undertake coordination activities in the project and overall guidance; also, the WP will guarantee that all control and reporting mechanisms are being applied according to the Quality Assurance Procedures.

WP2 – Chemoinformatics Framework Development for the drug database based on chemical descriptors and Pharmacophore modelling

The first step of chemoinformatics analysis is feature extraction, through which the compound is characterized by substructure fragments or other chemical descriptors.

Pharmacophore modelling is a widely used computer-aided drug design (CADD) approach that, in addition to docking methods, is used in virtual screening (VS) studies.

WP3 - Chemical similarity analysis and Machine learning models in QSAR.

The general protocol for QSAR models for drug discovery with cheminformatics and machine learning techniques will be developed.

WP 4 Druggability Assessment

Druggability is the likelihood of being able to modulate a target with a small-molecule drug is crucial in determining whether a drug discovery project progresses from 'hit' to 'lead'. The statistical models, a logistic regression model (TRAPP-LR) and a convolutional neural network model (TRAPP-CNN), for predicting druggability for the preselected candidates based on similarly statistical model and how it varies with changes in the spatial and physicochemical properties of a binding pocket.

WP5 Molecular Dynamics

Ionization equilibria in proteins are influenced by conformational flexibility, which can in principle be accounted for by molecular dynamics simulation. The ionization behavior of the treatable groups, and their pK values, is predicted under the assumption that the conformational ensemble is pH independent. The different structures according to the pH will be generated by molecular dynamics, each with a different protonation state of the protein molecule expected to be relevant at three pH regions.

WP6 - Definition, Setting Up and Running of the Platform will use the information gathered from the previous WP to specify, develop and deploy the information in the Communication Platform.

The main goal of this task is to define the conceptual architecture of the whole on line Platform with results obtained during the project.

WP7 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation will mediate communication and disseminate the project objectives and results, establishing an effective plan for arousing the interest of potential users, and ensuring an appropriate impact on the different groups and communities.

"

1.1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 Expected benefits and outcomes

The computer-aided drug design (CADD) will facilitate the focus of the research line for proper findings for drug compounds that binds and prevents the attachment/internalization of SARS-CoV-2 is decisively a perfect therapeutic option in this period of time constraint. In silico and bioinformatics approaches with their synergetic action has been effectively used by many studies to make a fast and more or less accurate prediction of potential drugs or inhibitors. The proposed project provides an alternative for an effective and multistep scheme for the conformational space explored by MD simulation by generating sets with different initial protonation states of the protein molecule leads to a better drug design and will elucidate the clinical testing results. It ensures that the project will result in the expected outcome according to its objectives and the program's outlines and all Work Packages (WPs) will jointly work according to their dependencies. Accordingly, application of the overall methodology developed in the project allows for initial high quality predictions of relative ligands activities.

The available data and results from the project will be organized in exportable open datasets that will be made openly available on a specific section of the web portal of the project to the scientific community for further investigation.

The computer-aided drug design (CADD) will facilitate the focus of the research line for proper findings for drug compounds that binds and prevents the attachment/internalization of SARS-CoV-2 is decisively a perfect therapeutic option in this period of time constraint. In silico and bioinformatics approaches with their synergetic action has been effectively used by many studies to make a fast and more or less accurate prediction of potential drugs or inhibitors. The proposed project provides an alternative for an effective and multistep scheme for the conformational space explored by MD simulation by generating sets with different initial protonation states of the protein molecule leads to a better drug design and will elucidate the clinical testing results. It ensures that the project will result in the expected outcome according to its objectives and the program's outlines and all Work Packages (WPs) will jointly work according to their dependencies. Accordingly, application of the overall methodology developed in the project allows for initial high quality predictions of relative ligands activities.

1.2 OBJECTIVES (LONG-TERM AND SHORT-TERM)

During the project period the stated objectives were set as the short term according to the period of realization of the tasks distributed in the WPs plan.

The long term objectives were developed during the project realization. Based on an obtained results and applied multiscale methods about creating a desirable and *sustainable* future plans for the formed team we have a *long-term* plan that

provides strategic direction and actions to achieve that in the next one year ahead.

1.3 RISKS AND ISSUES

The risks factors were monitors during the whole period. The unpredictable part of the project was a major task because of the unstable and dynamic situation in the European level caused by the pandemic. Due to fact that in the project plan the main source of the delivering the data were strongly dependent on the human activities for each task the project team was set up for realization a task between two or more participants. In the applied partitioning of WPS able to governor them as much as possible and make them as predictable as possible.

1.4 OUTCOMES

The main outcomes:

- Developed a database for natural compounds with a public access (<https://caddphytoinsilico.blog/>) with easy access to *compounds*.;
- Analyze protein-ligand interactions - this extension provides different utilities to analyze protein-ligand interactions. This tool is free of charge, the download link s=can be found here: <https://caddphytoinsilico.blog/>. The analysis of the protein-ligand interaction was performed using the new Protein-Ligand Interaction Analyzer Extension in SAMSON elements platform (<https://www.samson-connect.net>). The extension was developed using the SAMSON SDK for this project and is now freely available on SAMSON Connect, and it was used to compute radius of gyration, hydrogen bonds, ligand-surrounding residues, the solvent accessible surface area (SASA) and the contact area between the receptor and the ligand.
- Molecular docking –
The spike receptor binding domain (RBD) which is the object of our study was docked with the databased of 125 natural ligands and new binding modes were identified, as the most potent inhibitor candidates. The docking protocol based on of several steps were performed within AutodockVina for identification of the high-affinity binding mode, and for revealing more insights in the binding mechanisms between the phytochemicals and the RBD domain. The protocol yielded results presented below in details presents a perspective pipeline for the comprehensive studied based on a natural compound.
- Chemometric analysis - a cheminformatics procedure for a partitioning model based on 135 natural compounds attended as members of Flavonoids,

Saponins, Alkaloids, Terpenes and Triterpenes with drug-like features based on a descriptors pool has been developed. The knowledge about applicability of natural products as a unique source for development of new candidates towards deadly infectious disease is a contemporary challenge for drug discovery. We are proposing a partitioning scheme for unveiling drug-likeness candidates with properties which are important for prompt and efficient drug discovery process. In the present study, the vantage point is about the matching of descriptors to build the partitioning model applied to natural compounds with diversity in structures and complexity of action towards the severe diseases, as the actual SARS-CoV-2 virus. In the times of the de novo design techniques, such a tools based on a chemometric and symmetrical effect by the implied descriptors is another noticeable sigh for the power and level of the descriptors applicability in a drug discovery in establishing activity and target prediction pipeline for unknown drugs properties.

- Molecular dynamics based on variation in pH range in the RBD. To understand the effect of pH on the initial step of the infection of SARS-CoV-2 virus, we have studied at atomic level different structures of the Spike protein at different pHs. Molecular dynamics calculations are performed in order to predict new small drugs that could interfere the Spike-ACE2 interaction in a full range of pHs.
- Dissemination of the results – the results have been presented in few conferences.

1.6 TEAM MEMBER PROFILE

Dr. Miroslava Nedyalkova (Team Lider)

Research interest: Molecular dynamics, data analyses, ab initio dynamics

She is a fellow of prestigious Fulbright fellowship, as well she was recognized in 2018 as a fellow of Woman of Science supported by L'Oréal.

Dr. Sergio Madurga

Dr. Madurga currently works at the Department of Material Science and Physical Chemistry, University of Barcelona. Sergio does research in Soft Matter.

(<http://www.ub.edu/biophyschem/>)

Dr. Subramanyam Sappati

Dr. Sappati is computational chemist. Mainly focused on Nuclear Quantum Effects on H-bonded systems and electronic structure calculations of dye anchored. With strong background in Molecular dynamic simulations. He is working at Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research (IISER), Pune, India.

Dr. Julia Romanova

Dr. Romanova is a quantum chemist working in the field of material science and soft materials. In last years she is working as well as with the data science problems.

Dr. Mahdi Vasighi

Dr. Vasighi is an Assistant professor, Department of Computer Science and Information Technology, Institute for Advanced Studies in Basic Sciences, Zanjan, Iran. The main focus of his research interest is in Data science.

PhD candidate Haruna Luz Barazorda Ccahuana

Research interests of Ms. Barazorda is to understand the macromolecules' behavior at different pH and temperature conditions using computational biology and chemistry.

She is affiliated at Vicerrectorado de Investigación de la Universidad Católica de Santa María, Arequipa, Perú.

Prof. Vasil Simeonov

Prof. Simeonov is Chair of Analytical Chemistry. Laboratory of Chemometrics and Environmetrics at Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy. His main interest in chemometric application in different objects. A very well recognized scientist with more than 4200 citations.

2. KEY PROJECT ACTIVITIES

Summarized activity and/or topic

2.1 WP1- Project Management.

It is the objective of Project Management performed during overall project. This includes the following detailed objectives:

- Monitoring, tracking and controlling on the whole levels in the project. The deviations due to progress, costs, financial and, scheduling, changes. A status report based on weekly meetings with all team members. A weekly status report is an easy way to keep your team and stakeholders informed and manage expectations as a project progresses. By reviewing these status report based on:

- Work that's complete

- Work that's coming up

- Overall project completion and budget spent

- Managing the project according to approved plans for the WPs and budget frame
- Ensuring that the required and planned steps for the main work were prepared and delivered in a timely manner according to the final date of the project (31.03.2021)

- Implementing procedures for quality management based on a meeting with each member for the progress of the work

- The communication with the administration and financial office of the Sofia University.

2.2 WP2 – Cheminformatics Framework Development for the drug database based on chemical descriptors and Pharmacophore modelling

A cheminformatics procedure for a partitioning model based on 135 natural compounds attended as members of Flavonoids, Saponins, Alkaloids, Terpenes and Triterpenes with drug-like features based on a descriptors pool has been developed. The knowledge about applicability of natural products as a unique source for development of new candidates towards deadly infectious disease is a contemporary challenge for drug discovery. We are proposing a partitioning scheme for unveiling drug-likeness candidates with properties which are important for a prompt and efficient drug discovery process. In the present study, the vantage point is about the matching of descriptors to build the partitioning model applied to natural compounds with diversity in structures and complexity of action towards the severe diseases, as the actual SARS-CoV-2 virus.

In the times of the de novo design techniques, such tools based on a chemometric and symmetrical effect by the implied descriptors is another noticeable sign for the power and level of the descriptors applicability in a drug discovery in establishing activity and target prediction pipeline for unknown drugs properties.

The detailed explanation about the performed work planned in WP2 can be seen in the recently published paper: <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-8994/13/4/546>

2.3 WP3 - Chemical similarity analysis and Machine learning models in QSAR.

To facilitate the discovery process and to overcome the issues in the process of novel drugs development, the rational methods in the drug design in combination with the plethora of all the in silico methods is in a pivotal role. The discovery and screening of the natural drugs with the potential of a new perspective treating agents is the message in the present WP. It is about to make a combination with some methods as chemometric (multivariate statistical) for partitioning of a group (125 natural compounds) of natural compounds by the use of descriptors related to pharmacophores and drug-likeness indications which convey to designed and to facilitate an accountable partitioning network for the next level of treating and exploring the data. If a suitable partitioning with respect to the different chemical classes could be achieved, then a next step might be performed allowing more specific separation of some natural compounds using available descriptors. Finally, the specific partitioning could be used for prediction of important properties of the natural compounds studied based on the similarity between natural compound described by the descriptors. The molecular docking study has been as well performed to reveal the correlation between the docking scores and similarity pattern within the natural drugs candidates.

The data matrix has 125 rows (molecules) and 45 columns (descriptors)

A preliminary investigation about the data revealed that there is no zero or constant column. According to the difference between descriptors in range and scale (Fig. 1), a scaling procedure is essential. The range scaling was performed on the data in the variable direction (columns). In this way, each variable will be mapped on the range of 0 and 1.

Fig.1 Barplot of variables shows that a scaling method is needed to make the scale of the variables more similar for comparing or next analyses. (x-axis: variable number or column number, y-axis: descriptor value).

Principle component analysis was then applied to reveal hidden structures in samples and variables. At the first step, a cumulative plot of variance (Fig. 2) represents that the first three components can explain ~67% of variance in feature space. The first 12 components can reproduce around 90% of the system variance.

Fig.2 Cumulative plot of explained variance by principal components (PCs). The 2D score plot (Fig. 3) shows that there are some distinct clusters of samples in data space.

A dense cluster (or several dense clusters!) is/are placed on the left part of the plot. Further cluster analysis will be done at the next step but before doing that, for better

representation of the results, cluster regions are colored qualitatively. According to the 2D score plot, all four clusters are discriminated along the 1st PC direction. Fig. 4 shows the contribution of the descriptors to define 1st PC direction. The more absolute loading value means more importance to discriminate the molecules. The dense cluster (blue region) is spread along 2nd PC direction and also well separated from the yellow cluster. Same story can be said for the pink and green cluster along the 2nd PC direction. The importance of the variables (descriptors) to define 2nd PC can be investigated using second loading values (Fig. 5).

Fig.3 2D Score plot that explain around 56.5% of variation

According to the percent of explained variance by the first two PCs, the true structure of data may not be deduced well. Then the third PC and a 3D score plot could be more helpful. The resulted 3D score plot (Fig. 6) revealed that the dense cluster on the left part of the Fig. 3 is dispersed along the 3rd PC and formed several sub-clusters.

Fig.4 The 1st Loading values that define the first PC direction

Fig.5 The 2nd Loading values that define the first PC direction

Hence, there could be almost 8 clusters (Fig. 6) which could be a good guess to perform clustering methods like HCA or K-means.

Fig. 7 loading plot (PC1 vs PC2) reveal hidden structure in descriptor space.

Also, descriptor #13(Ui), #23(ESOL), #20(MLOGP2), #37(DLS_04) plus the group CATS2D descriptors (#1 to #7) have the most contribution to define PC2 direction and discrimination of the clusters along this PC.

Fig. 8 reveals that descriptors #17(TPSA(NO)), #18(TPSA(Tot)) and #38(DLS_05) have significant contribution to define PC3 and discrimination of clusters along this direction (for example the clusters A, B and C in Fig. 6).

To find similar patterns between molecules, K-means clustering was applied using first three PCs at k=10. Result of clustering is shown in the latent space (Fig 10).

Fig. 10 K-mean clustering of molecules using first three PCs.

The members of each clusters and the mean value of docking score for each cluster are reported in Table.1

Table 1. K-means clustering result (K=10)

Cluster id	# of members	Molecule id	Members	Mean Docking Score
1	13	4, 6, 19, 24, 30, 38, 43, 44, 71, 76, 95, 96, 122	'1,8-Cineole', '4-Terpinyl acetate', 'Anethole_ess_oil', 'Artemisia ketone', 'Beta-Thujone', 'Camphor', 'Cis-anethole', 'Citronellyl acetate', 'Isopinocampnone', 'L-Thujone', 'Pinocarvone', 'Piperitone', 'Trans-anethole'	-4.8923
2	23	9, 13, 34, 35, 36, 46, 48, 49, 50, 65, 68, 82, 83, 90, 98, 99, 113, 114, 115, 116, 117, 120, 123	'7-Methoxycryptopleurine', 'Alpha-Bisabolol', 'Blancoxanthone', 'Broussochalcone b', 'Camazulene', 'Curcumin', 'Demethoxycurcumin', 'Dihydrotanshinone i', 'Dihydrotanshinone', 'Guaiol', 'Isobavachalcone', 'Methyl tanshinonate',	-7.1783

			'Monodemethylcurcumin', 'Neobavaisoflavone', 'Psoralidin', 'Pyranojacareubin', 'Spathulenol', 'Tanshinone i', 'Tanshinone iia', 'Tanshinone IIb', 'Tau-Cadinol', 'Tetrahydrocurcumin', 'Viridiflorol'	
3	12	7, 29, 31, 41, 53, 58, 67, 97, 100, 107, 109, 112	'6-Oxoisoiguesterin', 'Beta-Sitosterol', 'Betulinic acid', ' Celastrol ', ' Epitaraxerol ', 'Friedelin', 'Iguesterin', ' Pristimerin ', 'Quadrangularic acid f', 'Sanggenol E', 'Schimperinone', ' Smilagenin '	-8.1083
4	7	17, 25, 72, 73, 91, 92, 111	' Amentoflavone ', 'Artocommunol e', 'Jubanine G', 'Jubanine H', 'Nummularine B', 'Ouabain', 'Silvestrol'	-7.4857
5	1	47	'Dehydroabieta-7-one'	-7.3000
6	19	2, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 32, 45, 55, 61, 63, 69, 75, 77, 80, 84, 93, 124, 125	'(E)-caryophyllene', '6,7- dehydroroyleanone', ' 10 '- hydroxyusambarensine ', 'Allo- Aromadendrene', 'Alpha- Cubebene', 'Alpha-selinene', 'Bicyclogermacrene', 'Cryptojaponol', 'Ferruginol', 'Gamma-Gurjunene', 'Germacrene b', 'Isoledene', 'Kazinol F', 'Ledene', 'Longifolen', 'Muurolene', 'Papyriflavonol A', 'Withanone', 'Xanthoangelol'	-6.7789
7	16	1, 3, 15, 23, 26, 28, 37, 39, 40, 54, 78, 79, 85, 104, 119, 121,	'(+)-artemisinic alcohol', '1- Cyclopentyl-2-propen-1-ol', 'Alpha- pinene', 'Artemisia alcohol', 'Ascaridole', 'Beta-pinene', 'Camphene', 'Carvacrol', 'Caryophyllene oxide', 'Eugenol', 'Limonene', 'Linalool', 'Myrcene', 'Sabinene', 'Terpinen-4-ol', 'Thujene'	-5.0875
8	8	52, 60, 86, 87, 88, 89, 94, 103	'Epigallocatechin gallate', 'Galocatechin gallate', 'Myricetin 3-(4''''-Galloylrhamnoside)', 'Myricetin 3-Neohesperidoside', 'Myricetin 3-Sambubioside', 'Myricetin 3''-Rhamnoside', 'Pectolarin', 'Rhoifolin'	-7.9000
9	5	11, 22, 64, 105, 106	'Akebia saponin c', 'Ardisia Saponin', ' Glycyrrhizin ', 'Ursane', ' Saikosaponin B2 '	-8.4600
10	21	5, 18, 20, 21, 27, 33, 42, 51, 56, 57, 59, 62, 66, 70, 74, 81, 101, 102, 108, 110, 118	'3-CE?-Friedelanol,mol2', 'Ampelopsin', 'APA', 'Apigenin', ' Baicalein ', 'Biochanin a', ' Chrysin_phyto ', 'Emodin_phyto', 'Fisetin', 'Formononetin', 'Gallic acid', 'Genistein', 'Hesperetin', 'Isoliquiritigenin', 'Kaempferol', 'Luteolin', 'Quercetin', 'Rhein_phyto',	-7.0190

Fig. 12 regression coefficient plot shows the contribution of descriptors in a linear system to predict docking score. (46th coefficient is for the constant value in regression)

Based on the regression results we can say that descriptor 34 to 41 can be linearly combined to predict the docking score values (strong linear relationship). This means that they can be assumed a spanning set for the docking score vector.

Linear Discriminant Analysis

By deciding a threshold for docking score we can have two types of molecules (Low Score / High Score). A threshold equal to -8.0 was decided, hence we have 22 compounds as low score and 103 molecules as high score ones.

Applying LDA results a coefficient vector which define a basis vector with maximum discriminatory power in feature space using linear combination of original features. It is clear that features 34 to 41 (all DLS descriptors) are the most important ones which can have most impact on docking score values. Among these descriptors, DLS_cons is the most important one.

Also, descriptors #3, #4, and #5 has somehow significant non-zero coefficient.

Fig. 13 regression coefficient plot shows the contribution of descriptors in a linear system to predict docking score. (46th coefficient is for the constant value in regression)

Accordance of LDA and MLR results show that these descriptors have the most impact

Self-Organizing Map

In order to investigate the hidden structure of the compounds in feature space and preserve the topology of the data, Self-Organizing Map as a nonlinear mapping method was performed on the scaled data set.

	29	67 58 53 7 109 31	97 41	100			106 64 105 11 22	111	92
			112		107	25			103 88 87 94
	55			125 124	75		91	73	86 89
84 14 80 77 2 15 69 63 63 2	61			10	93			72	17 52 60
				48	120 34 9				
	104 37 28 178 85				99	90 35 98 68		20	
	121 15	39		113	82		46 83 48	118	18
		119 26 3 79 23	54		117 65 13 116		66	59	
				49 114 115 50	123		5 102		
122 44 3 95 6 38 71 4 19 96 0 76			40						110 101 56 33 27 62 27 21 70 8 42 74

Fig. 14 Top Map (labels are sample ids) of a 10x10 SOM trained using scaled data.

Fig. 15 Top Map (labels are compound class abbreviation) of a 10x10 SOM trained using scaled data.

2.4 WP 4 Druggability Assessment

Docking results for phytochemicals on RDB of SARS-CoV2 S (spike protein) – druggability assessment for the RDB

A small dataset of 125 natural compounds (the obtained data are presented in the <https://research497632946.wordpress.com/wp-admin/post.php?post=2&action=edit>) was screened based on their structural and physicochemical properties as the criteria of selection. The generated input was based on a sets of descriptors (i.e., drug-like indices, pharmacophore descriptors,

and molecular properties) which were calculated by the AlvaDesc v.2 software (Milano, Italy) (<https://www.alvascience.com/alvadesc/>, access on 15 October 2020). The data for the descriptor set are available at <https://research497632946.wordpress.com/wp-admin/post.php?post=2&action=edit>

The target of our study was only the receptor-binding domain (RBD) extracted from PBD: 6m0j and the crystal structure was determined and published by Wand et al.³³

Molecular docking calculations with 125 ligands and the one receptor were conducted with Autodock Vin within the SAMSON platform. Hydrogens were conserved to both receptors and ligands. Both the number of flexible side chains was set to 25 and the number of modes was set to 100 with energy range = 3 kcal/mol (default value) The energy range is a maximum energy difference between the best binding mode and the unfavorable one displayed (kcal/mol). The energy (affinity) that differs more than 3 kcal/mol from the best mode are not saved among results. In the configuration file, the parameter called "exhaustiveness" was set to 8. The active pocket amino acid residues were used based on a degenerated data from a web server pocket detection. The broad table with the post docking analyses was deployed (<https://research497632946.wordpress.com/wp-admin/post.php?post=2&action=edit>)

The binding energy (kcal/mol) data and properties listed above allowed us to determine the flexibility and solvent accessible surface area (SASA) of ligand, receptors, and between the ligand-receptor. Properties, the Smilagenin is the

compound with the best docking score (picture, below). The information for the H-bonding was also presented in Table 2. Overall, the docking study discloses two different sets of ligands that bind at S1 and S2 domains of SARS-CoV-2S. We thought that if these molecules interact with either S1 or S2 domain strongly, it may perturb the hACE2-S protein complex interaction. So, based on the binding energy, we selected these top phytochemicals for our further in silico study.

Figure 1. The RBD with the top 3 ligands: Smilagenin, 10'-hydroxyusambarensine, and Celastrol

Figure 2. Hydrophobic pocket for the RBD pointed with the cycle for the receptor. Represented with Gaussian hydrophobic surface. The red-blue color scheme, red – hydrophobic, blue – hydrophilic

Figure 3. (A) the 3D structure of Smilagenin (B) RBD with Smilagenin as a ligand in the active binding site pocket view represented in Gaussian hydrophobic surface. The red-blue color scheme, red – hydrophobic, blue – hydrophilic

Figure 4. (A) the 3D structure of 10'-hydroxyusambarensine (B) RBD with 10'-hydroxyusambarensine as a ligand in the active binding site pocket view represented in the Gaussian hydrophobic surface. The red-blue color scheme, red – hydrophobic, blue – hydrophilic

Figure 5. (A) the 3D structure of Celastrol (B) RBD with Celastrol as a ligand in the active binding site pocket view represented in the gaussian hydrophobic surface. The red-blue color scheme, red – hydrophobic, blue – hydrophilic

Molecules that demonstrate the highest scores are key candidates for investigation.

The binding locations for explored ligands are crucial, the compounds contact key elements involved in S2 recognition and for the fusion of the viral and host cell membranes (S2 subunit), and could impact ACE2-S1 interactions as well.

2.5 WP 5 Molecular Dynamic Simulations

To understand the effect of pH on the initial step of the infection of SARS-CoV-2 virus, we have studied at atomic level different structures of the Spike protein at different pHs. Molecular dynamics and docking calculations are performed in order to predict new small drugs that could interfere the Spike-ACE2 interaction in a full range of pHs.

Computational Details

- Generation of different microstates of Spike at different pHs

The Semi-Grand Canonical Monte Carlo (SGCMC) program of the group was used to find different protonation states of titrable amino acids of the Spike protein at different pHs.[1-4]

The structure of the Spike protein was selected from pdb 6m0j. In this X-Ray structure, the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 virus is bound to the cell receptor ACE2.

The number of titrable residues in the RBD of the Spike in the selected pdb are: **9 ASP, 6 GLU, 1 HIS, 8 LYS and 9 ARG**. In this calculations, the titration of CYS and TYR were not considered as the pKa values are higher than the studied pH range.

In order to find different charge microstates, the SGCMC were run for 30000 steps of protonation/deprotonation of the Spike titrable residues at pHs 4, 5, 7 and 9.

At each pH, four independent microstates were selected. The obtained pH of the Spike is about 5.

- Molecular Dynamics Simulations.

For charge microstates obtained at pHs 4, 5, 7 and 9, four independent molecular dynamics simulations were carried out with the Gromacs v.2019.1 package.[5] The RBD of the spike protein was centred in a cubic box allowing 1.5 nm of minimum distance of surface protein to the sides of the simulation box. The system was solvated with TIP5P[6] waters. For each system, the total charge was neutralized with the appropriated quantity of Cl⁻ or Na⁺ ions. Initially a steepest-descent minimization was applied, followed by a 10 ns of MD simulation in the canonical (NVT) ensemble applying position restraints to alpha carbons of protein atoms. A temperature of 309.65 K was simulated using the V-rescale thermostat. Finally, a production simulation was carried out for each microstate of each pH with the isothermal-isobaric (NPT) ensemble using the Parrinello-Rahman barostat at 1 bar of reference pressure. A total of 16 MD simulations of 300 ns were performed. For each pH, the analysis for each of the four microstates of the four pH simulated.

RESULTS

Different analysis was performed in the trajectories of all the simulations in order to identify the role of the pH in the global structural properties of the RBD of Spike and in the surface contact with the ACE2 receptor. In particular, the RMSD (Root-Mean Squared Deviation), RG (Radius of Gyration), RMSF (Root-Mean Squared Fluctuation), SASA (Solvent Accessible Surface Area), HB (Number of Hydrogen Bonds), and RDF (Radial Distribution Function) analysis were performed using the Gromacs tools. In addition, calculation of Salt-Bridges (SB) and representation of images were performed using the Visual Molecular Dynamics (VMD) program [7].

In Figure 1, it is analysed the RMSD of the BRD domain of the Spike protein at 4 different pHs. It could be seen that the protein remains stable after the first nanoseconds of simulation. No significant difference were observed among the different pHs. The RMSD average value of the BRD domain seems to be independently of the simulated pH.

It could be seen in Fig. 2 the average RG of the four simulations for each pH. In all cases, RG profiles show a stable value during all NPT simulations. It could be seen that the average value of the RG is slightly greater at lower pHs. Thus, the global effect of the pH over the conformation is to increase the size of the BRD at more acidic pHs.

Figure 3 shows the average SASA values for the 4 simulations of the 4 pHs during the 300 ns. It can be seen a stable value during all simulation trajectory. The global tendency is that higher values of SASA are obtained for simulations corresponding to lower pHs. This behaviour corroborates the explanation for RG analysis. Lower pHs makes the protein to increase in size slightly having greater RG and SASA values.

It could be seen in Fig. 4 the RMSF of the residues of the Spike protein at different pHs. There are four regions where the fluctuations of the residues are greater, in the regions 330-335, 365-375, 470-490 and 515-522. The general behaviour is that the fluctuation of the residue is independent of the simulated pH. However, only in one region of high fluctuation, 365-375, there is a visible effect of pH in the degree of fluctuation. It could be seen that acidic pHs make higher fluctuation in this previous region. Thus, the effect of pH over the conformational properties of the BRD of Spike is only located in the region of residues 365 to 375.

References

- [1] Madurga, S.; Garcés, J. L.; Companys, E.; Rey-Castro, C.; Salvador, J.; Galceran, J.; Vilaseca, E.; Puy, J.; Mas, F. Ion binding to polyelectrolytes: Monte Carlo simulations versus classical mean field theories. *Theoretical Chemistry Accounts* 2009, 123, 127–135.
- [2] Madurga, S.; Rey-Castro, C.; Pastor, I.; Vilaseca, E.; David, C.; Garcés, J. L.; Puy, J.; Mas, F. A semi-grand canonical Monte Carlo simulation model for ion binding to ionizable surfaces: Proton binding of carboxylated latex particles as a case study. *The Journal of chemical physics* 2011, 135, 184103.
- [3] Blanco, P. M.; Madurga, S.; Mas, F.; Garcés, J. L. Coupling of charge regulation and conformational equilibria in linear weak polyelectrolytes: Treatment of long-range interactions via effective short-ranged and pH-dependent interaction parameters. *Polymers* 2018, 10, 811.
- [4] Blanco, P. M.; Madurga, S.; Narambuena, C. F.; Mas, F.; Garcés, J. L. Role of charge regulation and fluctuations in the conformational and mechanical properties of weak flexible polyelectrolytes. *Polymers* 2019, 11, 1962.
- [5] Van Der Spoel, D.; Lindahl, E.; Hess, B.; Groenhof, G.; Mark, A. E.; Berendsen, H. J.

GROMACS: fast, flexible, and free. Journal of computational chemistry 2005, 26, 1701–1718.

[6] Mahoney, M. W.; Jorgensen, W. L. Diffusion constant of the TIP5P model of liquid water. The Journal of Chemical Physics 2001, 114, 363–366.

[7] Humphrey, W.; Dalke, A.; Schulten, K., et al. VMD: visual molecular dynamics. Journal of molecular graphics 1996, 14, 33–38.

2.6 WP6 - Definition, Setting Up and Running of the Platform -

https://caddphytoinsilico.blog/?preview_id=2&preview_nonce=d3d0a581e2&preview=true

Platform **cadd.phyto.insilico**

The developed platform with implemented data have access by the following link above: The Open Data Platform, developed by the team with input from the data obtained from different analyses was a dissemination convey platform in the free open web available to all researchers. The Platform has been designed to easily facilitate the data downloads creation of tables, charts, graphs on the platform for visualizations and automation of downloads in the uploaded format, the preferred machine-to-machine exchange format.

2.7 WP7 - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation will mediate communication and disseminate the project objectives and results, establishing an effective plan for arousing the interest of potential users, and ensuring an appropriate impact on the different groups and communities.

The obtained results have been presented in the following conferences:

- 1. ACS Spring 2021, April 5-30, 2021 - PAPER ID: 3551619
PAPER TITLE: "Computer-aided drug designing platform towards the enigma SARS-CoV-2 spike protein of COVID-19", DIVISION/COMMITTEE: COMP (POSTER presented in Supporting Information);
- 2. Hünfeld 2021: Workshop on Computer Simulation and Theory of Macromolecules <https://www.mpibpc.mpg.de/grubmueller/huenfeld>; (POSTER presented in Supporting Information);
-
- 3. Co-creating EOSC Webinars: Fighting COVID-19 with Open Science": Date Time: Apr 13, 2021 11:00 AM, (POSTER presented in Supporting Information);
- 4. Virtual Conference on Chemistry and its Applications (VCCA-2021) will be held from 9 to 13 August 2021. It is organised by the Computational Chemistry Group of the University of Mauritius. – UPCOMING EVENT
- 5. You are now a member in the group 'RDA-COVID19-Clinical' located at <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-covid19-clinical>
- 6. You are now a member in the group 'RDA-COVID19-Omics' located at <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-covid19-omics>
- 7. Participation in subgroup of the RDA-COVID-19 working group focusing on Clinical.

- In the following link you can see the members list: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/node/68845/members>
- Co-chair assigned: Anne Cambon-Thomsen
- Moderator(s): Sergio Bonini, Andrea Jackson-Dipina, Dawei Lin, Christian Ohmann
- Email: rda-covid19-clinical@rda-groups.org
- Useful Information for RDA COVID-19 Clinical Subgroup
- <https://www.rd-alliance.org/group/rda-covid19-clinical/post/partitioning-pattern-natural-products-based-molecular-properties>

2.8 Density Functional study for obtaining the new descriptors based on electronic structure of the favorable drug candidates based on Docking results.

Computational protocol

All molecules are optimized with the B3LYP functional and 6-31G* basis set. The solvent effects were taken into account implicitly by using the IEPCM of water ($\epsilon_0=80.4$). The optimized structures were subject to frequency analysis in order to verify that they represent minima on the potential energy surface. All calculations were performed with Gaussian 09. The MOs are visualized by using GaussView 6 and isosurface value of 0.02.

Results

Table 1 summarizes the thermochemistry results, dipole moments and isotropic polarizability for the investigated compounds. The results indicated that among all ligands Saikosaponin B2 is characterized with highest value of the dipole moment – about seven times higher than the dipole moment of Celastrol and 40 times higher than in the case of Smilagenin. With respect to the dipole moment the ligands order as Smilagenin < 10-hydroxyusambarensine < Amentoflavone < Celastrol << Saikosaponin_B2. Saikosaponin B2 possess also highest polarizability in the series, which can be explained by its molecular size. Its structure represents (много е странна структурата – провери я) a complex between two molecules. The polarizability trend approximately follows the dipole moments one and is as follows: Smilagenin < 10-hydroxyusambarensine ~ Celastrol < Amentoflavone < Saikosaponin_B2.

Table 2 contains the frontier molecular orbitals (FMO) results and reactivity indices for all ligands. Here, again Saikosaponin_B2 stands out as structure with unique properties, namely it has highest HOMO and lowest LUMO in the series and respectively very small band gap (0.92 eV). This is in agreement with the charge transfer character of the complex (**Figure 1**). The Saikosaponin_B2 is characterized also with lowest global hardness, highest softness and highest global electrophilicity. The Smilagenin on the other hand possess very low HOMO and even positive LUMO, which give rise to very large bandgap. The latter is consistent non-conjugated skeleton of the compound and the presence of only sp^3 carbons in its structure. Among all ligands Smilagenin show highest global hardness, lowest softness and lowest global electrophilicity. It worth to note that the reactivity indices for Smilagenin are closer in quantitative aspect to the reactivity indices of 10-hydroxyusambarensine, Celastrol and Amentoflavone, while Saikosaponin_B2 is a real "outlier". The best electron donor and acceptor in the series are Smilagenin and Saikosaponin_B2, respectively.

The results for the Mulliken charges in the ligands indicate that the most nucleophilic atoms in 10-hydroxyusambarensine are the nitrogen in the five-membered heterocycles and that the nitrogen in the C=O functionalized part of the molecules is a stronger nucleophile. For Amentoflavone, Smilagenin and Celastrol, the nucleophilic atoms are all oxygens from the carbonyl groups. Saikosaponin_B2 also contains plenty of C=O groups and therefore high number of oxygens as nucleophilic centers. The best nucleophile among them is located in one of the molecules from the Saikosaponin_B2 complex and has charge -0.746. The highest positive charges in the ligands are observed for the carbons from the carbonyl group. However, in 10-hydroxyusambarensine, Amentoflavone, Saikosaponin_B2 and Smilagenin there are no carbon electrophilic centers. In opposite, there are two sp^3 hybridized secondary carbons in the central six-membered rings of Celastrol that are highly positive and can be regarded as strong electrophile attractors.

Table 1. Thermochemistry results, dipole moment μ [D] and isotropic polarizability α [Bohr³] obtained at the IEPCM/B3LYP/6-31G* level of theory.

	ZPVE (a.u./particle)	E _{tot} [a.u.]	H [a.u.]	G [a.u.]	μ [D]	α [Bohr ³]
10-hydroxyusambarensine	- 1415.6883 26	- 1415.66066 1	- 1415.65971 7	- -1415.747415	2.70	453.14
Amentoflavone	- 1905.8901 24	- 1905.85833 6	- 1905.85739 2	- -1905.954990	4.96	523.01
Celastrol	- 1428.2316 81	- 1428.20099 1	- 1428.20004 7	- -1428.289478	9.46	451.46
Saikosaponin_B2	- 2610.6288 33	- 2610.57168 6	- 2610.57074 2	- -2610.721044	62.9 7	648.57
Smilagenin	- 1280.3855 95	- 1280.35765 2	- 1280.35670 8	- -1280.441287	1.56	366.47

ZPVE – Sum of electronic and zero-point, E_{tot} - Sum of electronic and thermal energies, H - Sum of electronic and thermal enthalpies, G - Sum of electronic and thermal free Energies.

Table 2. The energy of the HOMO and LUMO orbitals, the HOMO-LUMO bandgap $\Delta E = E_{LUMO} - E_{HOMO}$, ionization potential $I = -E_{HOMO}$, electron affinity $E = -E_{LUMO}$, electronegativity $\chi = -1/2(E_{HOMO} + E_{LUMO})$, global hardness $\eta = -1/2(E_{HOMO} - E_{LUMO})$, softness $\delta = 1/\eta$, global electrophilicity index $\omega = \chi^2/2\eta$. The results are obtained at the IEPCM/B3LYP/6-31G* level of theory.

	HOMO [eV]	LUMO [eV]	ΔE [eV]	I [eV]	A [eV]	χ [eV]	η [eV]	δ [eV]	ω [eV]
10-hydroxyusambarensine	-5.34	-1.21	4.12	5.3 4	1.2 1	3.2 7	2.06	0.48	2.60
Amentoflavone	-5.90	-1.86	4.04	5.9 0	1.8 6	3.8 8	2.02	0.50	3.73
Celastrol	-5.47	-2.44	3.03	5.4 7	2.4 4	3.9 5	1.52	0.66	5.15
Saikosaponin_B2	-4.05	-3.13	0.92	4.0 5	3.1 3	3.5 9	0.46	2.17	13.9 6

					-				
				6.8	1.9	2.4			
Smilagenin	-6.85	1.96	8.81	5	6	4	4.40	0.23	0.68

Figure 1. MOs for the investigated compounds.

Figure 2. Mulliken charges in the investigated compounds. The hydrogens are omitted for clarity.

10-hydroxyusambarensin
e

Amentoflavone

Celastrol

Saikosaponin_B2

Smilagenin

COSTS SUMMARY

Budget Plan	
Personnel costs	€ 25 197.69
Direct costs of providing financial management	€ 1 102.88
conference fees	€ 230.00
publications fees	€ 1 380.74
	€ -
Technical equipment and web hosting	€ 12 089.26
COSTS	
<p>All the cost was verified by the University of Sofia counter office, and according to the Bulgaria Legislation law.</p>	

PUBLICATIONS /accepted and submitted/

1. Nedyalkova, M.; Simeonov, V. Partitioning Pattern of Natural Products Based on Molecular Properties Descriptors Representing Drug-Likeness. *Symmetry* **2021**, *13*, 546.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/sym13040546> <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-8994/13/4/546>
More two articles are in preparation.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION:

POSTERS

Computer-aided drug designing platform towards the enigma SARS-CoV-2 spike protein of COVID-19

Miroslava Nedyalkova, Subrahmanyam Sappati and Vasil Simeonov
 Sofia University, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia, Bulgaria
 nhmn@chem.uni-sofia.bg

Docking scores

Selected Inhibitors

Flavonoids	Docking Score	Terpenes	Docking Score
Amentoflavone (AMN)	-8.7500	Glycyrrhizin (GLR)	-8.7
Psoralidin (PSR)	-7.475	Allo-Aromadendrene (ALR)	-5.8667
Apigenin (APG)	-7.6333	α -selinene (ALS)	-5.8667

The spike receptor binding domain (RBD) were docked with the database of forty ligands and new binding modes were identified, as the most potent inhibitor candidates. The docking protocol based on several steps were performed within Autodock Vina for identification of the high-affinity binding mode, and for revealing more insights in the binding mechanisms between the phytochemicals and the RBD domain the Protein-Ligand interaction analyzer has been developed. To assess the performance of the docking protocol, molecular dynamics and metadynamics simulations techniques has been chosen as a validation tools for the best poses.

RMSD & Rg

The authors acknowledge the financial support of the EOS secretariat.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-05-2018-2019, grant Agreement number 831644.

Molecular Docking Study and Multivariate Statistical Approach of Natural Compounds Inhibition Effects on the SARS-CoV2 Spike Protein

Miroslava Nedyalkova, Mahdi Vasighi and Vasil Simeonov
Sofia University, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia, Bulgaria
nhmn@chem.uni-sofia.bg

Hünfeldt 2021: Workshop on Computer Simulation and Theory of Macromolecules

April 23-24, 2021

Molecule docking Calculations

- Molecular docking of the dataset was conducted by **Autodock Vin** within the **SAMSON** platform.
- **AlvaDesc** for the descriptors dataset

Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) (EC:3.4.17.23) is a transmembrane protein that is considered as a receptor for spike protein binding of novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV2). Since nonspecific medication is available to treat COVID-19, designing a new drug is important and essential. In this regard, in silico method plays an important role, as it is rapid and cost-effective compared to the trial and error methods using experimental studies. Natural products are available to combat coronavirus affected patients, in the present alarming situation. The study is based on 40 phytochemicals, which have been selected as small molecules in the molecular docking study of the spike protein of SARS-CoV2 (RBD) with its human receptor ACE2 molecule

Natural product name	Affinity [kcal/mol]	Predicted Inhibition Constant (Ki) (nM)	Classes
Smilagenin	-10.5	0.020111629	saponin
10'-hydroxysambarensine	-10.2	0.033369427	alkaloids
Celastrin	-9.1	0.213626083	flavonoids
Saikosaponin B2	-9.1	0.213626083	saponin
Amentoflavone	-9	0.252803465	flavonoids
Baicalitin	-8.8	0.354450656	flavonoids
Epitaraxerol	-8.8	0.354450656	flavonoids
Glycyrrhizin	-8.7	0.419620104	flavonoid
Pristimerin	-8.6	0.496771635	flavonoids
Chrysin_phyto	-8.5	0.588108278	flavonoids

The authors acknowledge the financial support of the EOS secretariat.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-05-2018-201 grant Agreement number 831644.

The effect of pH on the SARS-CoV-2-spike receptor binding domain – molecular dynamic study

Miroslava Nedyalkova, Haruna Varazorda, Sergio Madurga
Sofia University, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Sofia, Bulgaria
nhmn@chem.uni-sofia.bg

Co-creating EOSC Webinars: Fighting COVID-19 with
Open Science
13/4/2021

RBD is a protein domain of 220 residues, it has nine cysteine residues (eight of them forming disulfide bonds) (Fig. 1) and two N-glycosylation sites (N331 and N343). The addition of glycan moieties might have a relevant role on the in vivo protein folding process, on the dynamics, stability and solvent accessibility of RBD and also on its immunogenicity^{21,22}. It has been also previously described that mutations in specific residues might have significant effects on the RBD stability²³. RBD is not a globular protein domain; it has a central twisted antiparallel beta-sheet formed by five strands decorated with secondary structure elements (short helices and strands) and loops¹⁹. The secondary structure analysis of the protein shows 12.4% helix, 33.0% sheet, 19.1% turn, and 35.6% coil.

To understand the effect of pH on the initial step of the infection of SARS-CoV-2 virus, we have studied at atomic level different structures of the Spike protein at different pHs. Molecular dynamics and docking calculations are performed in order to predict new small drugs that could interfere the Spike-ACE2 interaction in a full range of pHs. Molecular dynamics simulations suggest that local motions of the RBD are important to be tracked. However, part of the time RBD domain is buried within the rest of the Spike protein, and this process is mediated by protein motions of high amplitude.

Computational Details

- Generation of different microstates of Spike at different pHs

The Semi-Grand Canonical Monte Carlo (SGCMC) program of the group was used to find different protonation states of ionizable amino acids of the Spike protein at different pHs^[1,4]. The structure of the Spike protein was selected from pdb (6x01). In this X-ray structure, the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 virus is bound to the cell-receptor ACE2. The number of ionizable residues in the RBD of the Spike in the selected path are: 9 ASP, 6 GLU, 3 HIS, 8 TYR and 9 ARG. In this calculation, the titration of CYS and TRP were not considered as the pKa values are higher than the studied pH range. In order to find different charge microstates, the SGCMC were run for 30000 steps of protonation/deprotonation of the Spike ionizable residues at pHs 4, 5, 7 and 9.

- Molecular Dynamics Simulations.

For charge microstates obtained at pHs 4, 5, 7 and 9, four independent molecular dynamics simulations were carried out with the Gromacs v2019.2 package^[2]. The RBD of the spike protein was centered in a cubic box allowing 1.5 nm of minimum distance of surface protein to the sides of the simulation box. The system was solvated with TIP3P^[3] waters. For each system, the total charge was neutralized with the appropriated quantity of Cl⁻ or Na⁺ ions. Initially a steepest descent minimization was applied, followed by a 50 ns of MD simulation in the canonical (NVT) ensemble applying position restraints to alpha carbons of protein atoms. A temperature of 300 K was simulated using the V-rescale thermostat. Finally, a production simulation were carried out for each microstate of each pH with the restricted restraints (RFT) ensemble using the Parrinello-Rahman barostat at 1 bar of reference pressure. A total of 50 MD simulations of 300 ns were performed. For each pH, the analysis for each of the four microstates of the four pH simulated.

Figure 1. RMSF of the BRD domain of Spike protein at different pHs.

Figure 2. RMSF of the BRD domain of the Spike protein at different pHs.

Figure 3. RMS of the BRD domain of Spike protein at different pHs.

Figure 4. SASA of the BRD domain of the Spike protein at different pHs.

It could be seen in Fig. 4 the RMSF of the residues of the Spike protein at different pHs. There are four regions where the fluctuations of the residues are greater, in the regions 330-335, 365-375, 470-490 and 515-522. The general behaviour is that the fluctuation of the residue is independent of the simulated pH. However, only in one region of high fluctuation, 365-375, there is a visible effect of pH in the degree of fluctuation. It could be seen that acidic pHs makes higher fluctuation in this previous region. Thus, the effect of pH over the conformational properties of the BRD of Spike is only located in the region of residues 365 to 375.

The authors acknowledge the financial support of the EOS secretariat.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-05-2018-201 grant Agreement number 831644.

The all members are deeply acknowledging about the opportunity for working on this challenging topic. We do hope that we will give a dust in science going forward in tackling the battle with the severed disease.